

**Selections from the speeches of Mohammad Reza
Pahlavi, Shah of Iran**

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1- Speech by Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, Shah of Iran, on November 13, 1941, on the occasion of the opening of the thirteenth session of the Majlis:

The end of the twelfth session of the Majlis coincided with extraordinary events that were contrary to expectations and had a profound impact on the affairs of the country. The representatives of that period, like the general public, despite being affected by those events, were generally performing their duties wisely and with dignity.

As for the internal affairs, the government's policy should be to pursue social and economic reforms in accordance with the requirements, which requires, from the legislative side, diligent cooperation between the Majlis and the government by all means. In particular, I see the need to emphasize the absolute necessity of national unity.

I call upon the sons of the nation and all segments of society to perform their duties with a spirit of responsibility that requires public interest with care and in accordance with the national spirit. The best way to do this is to support the strength and stability of the government. To achieve this goal, the government and the Majlis must do everything they can seriously and strive to achieve this goal immediately and with full legal authority, in all matters, especially in health and education, which is the basis of the new life of the Iranian people.

2- Speech by Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, Shah of Iran, on July 17, 1947, on the occasion of the opening of the fifteenth session of the Majlis:

Unlike expectations, the opening of the National Consultative Assembly in its fifteenth session was delayed for a period of time. This delay, as everyone knows, was the result of events that took place in the fourteenth parliament and led to insecurity and unfortunate events. The sadness and turmoil that we are going through and that has befallen the country will not disappear from our memory. Now, after God's pleasure and thanks to our will, the efforts of the government, and the national sentiments of the Iranian people, the general situation has returned to normal, and we are opening the legislative body.

In foreign policy, we are pleased to say that our relations with friendly and neighboring countries, especially the great powers, are based on the principle of reciprocity and mutual respect. With Iran's participation in the United Nations, world peace can be supported and the rights of nations can be preserved.

In internal affairs, the policy of our government is based on trying to improve life and achieve public welfare and progress, which is what the country needs badly in various fields. Of course, this goal must be achieved through economic, social, and administrative reforms. In particular, we have directed the government to consider the necessary reforms in all affairs and needs of the country in the program it presents to the parliament. We expect representatives of the nation not to abandon their efforts in enacting beneficial laws and sincere cooperation. We also perform our duties for the benefit of the homeland with full attention and care in every case, and we wish to provide happiness and success in all ways.

3- Speech by Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, Shah of Iran, on February 9, 1950, on the occasion of the opening of the first session of the Senate and the sixteenth session of the Majlis:

By the grace of God Almighty and with great pleasure, and for the first time in the history of Iran, we are opening the first session of the Senate and the sixteenth session of the Majlis.

As the representatives of the people are well aware, the World War and its consequences have caused untold suffering in the past eight years, any of which could have led our country to a destructive catastrophe. In those years, we made tremendous efforts and engaged in fighting these problems, repelling dangers, and eliminating them.

It can be said that these measures strengthened the constitutional foundations of Iran and saved the country from the danger of internal chaos and the dependence of the ruling classes that were aiming to lead the country to an absolute government. We are confident that a ground will be provided for the reform of affairs by all means, which will enable us to remove these obstacles and obtain new opportunities. Let us pay attention to our society, and we must strive tirelessly to prepare for the prosperity and well-being of the nation.

Our approach in foreign policy is to strengthen and strengthen friendly relations on the basis of mutual respect with our neighbors and all countries of the world. As before, our country is committed to and concerned with the principles and rules of the UN Charter, which we consider to be the only guarantee of peace.

In domestic policy, I would like to briefly clarify that our government will be serious in the first phase to take effective measures to extract the resources of the country's wealth and distribute them more fairly by taking into account the principles of social guidance among the general public. Special attention should be paid to the welfare of the working class and farmers, so that our country will be at the level of developed countries. Our main and final goal, which we have mentioned repeatedly, is to provide food, clothing, housing, health, and culture for everyone, as well as in reducing the cost of living. Our government will propose bills to the parliament in due course. Fortunately, the best tool available to us to understand this goal is the implementation of the seven-year plan, which has been carefully formulated and studied by experts. This program, which is the basis of state reforms in all social matters, must be implemented.

Our country has a long history in which there have been many periods of hardship and difficulty, including the period of eight years to this time. However, now we can say that with the help of God, we can implement this program with a little patience. Finally, the ancient civilization, the sense of nationalism, and the courage of our nation, which has always overcome problems, will come out of the bottleneck with its fruits and goodness.

The other part of our focus will be on the struggle against the devil of corruption and the establishment of social justice in all aspects of the country. We are in a relentless struggle and will not give up until we root out the roots of corruption and sow goodness and sow prosperity in society instead.

In the field of building security forces, fortunately, we must say that our peace-loving army is progressing and developing regularly and reliably, and security is better stabilized in the country.

Regarding charitable organizations, effective steps have been taken on a solid basis, which makes us happy. Of course, we will try to make these organizations broader, more beneficial, and have a more distinctive description.

Our government will take positive, beneficial, and bold steps in the way of advancing this ideology, which we are confident will be recognized and endorsed by the deputies. We have a duty from God Almighty to continuously protect our country and the success of the representatives in fulfilling their legal duties.

4- Speech by Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, Shah of Iran, on October 7, 1951, on the occasion of the opening of the second session of the Iranian Senate:

By the grace of God Almighty, we are opening the second session of the Senate. It is a very happy occasion that, as a result of coordination between the Majlis and the government and in line with the general trends, major steps have been taken to achieve the interests of Iran. Nationalization of oil has become a legitimate law throughout the country, and we hope that the efforts of the government and the nation will achieve the desired result.

In order for harmony to take a permanent form, it is necessary to prevent misleading propaganda aimed at undermining the basis of the national state, and to preserve it under the unity of national traditions.

The approach of our government in domestic policy is to expand social justice, reform the judiciary, achieve a balance in the general budget of the state, distribute wealth fairly and use natural resources, encourage competent and

patriotic youth, and finally provide welfare for the working class, especially farmers and workers.

In foreign affairs, as we have said repeatedly, the government will maintain friendly and good relations with all countries of the world on the basis of mutual respect, in accordance with the UN Charter.

The Senate is concerned with important national reforms, including the innovative approach it has adopted in proposing the reform of municipal independence, and the adoption of laws that facilitate the transfer of public works to the people.

We hope that this goal will be achieved with good faith, the serious and sincere cooperation of the parliaments, and the sincere interest of the people in implementing and preserving the principles of the constitutional movement, and that our ancient country, God willing, will overcome all problems and achieve the position it deserves.